

Survey Summary: Review of the James Joyce Digital Archive (2018-).

July–September 2022.

Completed responses: 63.

1. Please identify your professional occupation. *If you have published on Joyce, please choose “academic”, unless you are a student.							
Answer Choices						Response Percent	Response Total
1	Academic					65.08%	41
2	Non-academic					15.87%	10
3	Graduate/Postgraduate					7.94%	5
4	Undergraduate					0.00%	0
5	Other (please specify):					11.11%	7
Analysis	Minimum:	1.00	Mean:	1.76	Std. Deviation:	1.29	answered
	Maximum:	5.00	Variance:	1.67	Std. Error:	0.16	skipped
	Satisfaction Rate:	19.05					
Other (please specify): (7)							
1	Long-time amateur Joycean.						
2	High school teacher, Ph.D. candidate, <i>Wake</i> reading group member and administrator.						
3	Ph.D.						
4	Retired academic, painter, poet, swimmer, book reviewer, caretaker for elderly artist friend, miniature gardener, zen meditator.						
5	Reading Group facilitator.						
6	Retired, non-academic, postgraduate.						
7	Independent scholar with a Ph.D. in English and comparative literature.						

2. Do you remember how you discovered the JJDA?							
Answer Choices						Response Percent	Response Total
1	Academic/Professional network					50.00%	31
2	Recommended literature/cited reference					11.29%	7
3	Internet search					16.13%	10
4	Hearsay					8.06%	5

2. Do you remember how you discovered the JJDA?

5	Other (please specify):		14.52%	9				
Analysis	Minimum:	1.00	Mean:	2.26	Std. Deviation:	1.49	answered	62
	Maximum:	5.00	Variance:	2.22	Std. Error:	0.19	skipped	1
	Satisfaction Rate:	31.45						
Other (please specify): (9)								
1	From the mouth of the Beast himself (Danis Rose).							
2	International Joyce Symposium, 2018, Antwerp.							
3	International Joyce Symposium, 2018, Antwerp.							
4	To my regret, I have only just discovered it: a result of your email.							
5	<i>Finnegans Wake</i> reading group.							
6	<i>Finnegans Wake</i> reading group.							
7	Twitter/X.							
8	It was mentioned to me at the launch of Danis O’Hanlon’s “restored text” of <i>Finnegans Wake</i> .							
9	Referred by Des Gunning of Joyceborough.							

3. In what capacity do you engage with the JJDA?

Answer Choices							Response Percent	Response Total
1	Academic/Professional		53.97%	34				
2	Personal		14.29%	9				
3	A little of everything, actually		23.81%	15				
4	Other (please specify):		7.94%	5				
Analysis	Minimum:	1.00	Mean:	1.86	Std. Deviation:	1.04	answered	63
	Maximum:	4.00	Variance:	1.07	Std. Error:	0.13	skipped	0
	Satisfaction Rate:	28.57						
Other (please specify): (5)								
1	Academic/Professional and occasional contributor.							
2	Future tense only.							
3	I use it as convenor/facilitator of <i>Finnegans Wake</i> Reading Group (xxx), as a member of the 'Thirsty Scholars' <i>Finnegans Wake</i> Reading Group (xxx), and as an occasional consultant to the Brooklyn <i>Finnegans Wake</i> Sunday School.							

3. In what capacity do you engage with the JJDA?

- | | |
|---|---|
| 4 | I prepare monthly notes for circulation in the Melbourne <i>Finnegans Wake</i> Reading Group. |
| 5 | Independent scholarship. |

4. How often do you engage with the JJDA on average?

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Response Total					
1	Every day	4.76%	3					
2	A few times a week	23.81%	15					
3	About once a week	9.52%	6					
4	A few times a month	20.63%	13					
5	Once a month	14.29%	9					
6	Less than once a month	26.98%	17					
Analysis	Minimum:	1.00	Mean:	3.97	Std. Deviation:	1.64	answered	63
	Maximum:	6.00	Variance:	2.70	Std. Error:	0.21		
	Satisfaction Rate:	59.37					skipped	0

5. Which volume of the JJDA do you spend most of your time on?

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Response Total					
1	Ulysses	26.98%	17					
2	Finnegans Wake	50.79%	32					
3	I like to mix and match	20.63%	13					
4	I'm there for something else (you have an option to elaborate)	1.59%	1					
Analysis	Minimum:	1.00	Mean:	1.97	Std. Deviation:	0.73	answered	63
	Maximum:	4.00	Variance:	0.54	Std. Error:	0.09		
	Satisfaction Rate:	32.28					skipped	0

I'm there for something else (you have an option to elaborate) (1)

- | | |
|---|---|
| 1 | The pages listing Joyce's notebook sources for <i>Ulysses</i> and <i>Finnegans Wake</i> . |
|---|---|

6. Do you customarily use any other printed resource in tandem with the JJDA?

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Response Total					
1	Not usually. I can find everything I need on the site.		10.53% 6					
2	Yes, but it is a matter of choice.		49.12% 28					
3	Yes. Just one more source (please specify below)		15.79% 9					
4	There are a few sources that complement the JJDA beautifully (please give examples below)		24.56% 14					
Analysis	Minimum:	1.00	Mean:	2.54	Std. Deviation:	0.97	answered	57
	Maximum:	4.00	Variance:	0.95	Std. Error:	0.13		
	Satisfaction Rate:	51.46					skipped	6

Examples of additional sources (if any) (36)

1	Rosenbach Manuscript, Gabler, Oxford World's Classics edition, A Review of Three Texts.
2	<i>JJA</i> (Garland, 1978); FW first edition (1939); Finnegans Wake, translation by Erik Bindervoet & Robbert-Jan Henkes, the appendix (2002).
3	Finwake.com, McHugh's FW Annotations, the printed <i>JJA</i> , riverrun.org (Joyce Tools).
4	<i>JJA</i> .
5	<i>JJA</i> , Letters; online: <i>Ulysses</i> scans at the Modernist Versions Project.
6	<i>JJA</i> , ed. Michael Groden et al, is a great resource but not as available for me. The JJDA can be accessed from everywhere.
7	NLI 2002 Joyce Papers online catalogue, James Joyce's Correspondence.org, fweet, GJS, JSTOR, and various books related to the manuscripts/notes/etc.
8	Gifford's notes.
9	FWEET and Joyce's Ulysses Concordance: https://joyceconcordance.andreamoro.net .
10	FWEET; McHugh.
11	<i>JJA</i> , plus several articles and books of genetic criticism.
12	Gabler's CSE.
13	<i>JJA</i> .
14	<i>JJA</i> .
15	McHugh's Annotations, finwake.org.

6. Do you customarily use any other printed resource in tandem with the JJDA?

16	<i>JJA</i> .
17	<i>JJA</i> / Annotations to <i>Finnegans Wake</i> .
18	McHugh's "Annotations", Fweet, Wake Rites-Gibson, Dublin's Joyce-Kenner, War & Peace in the Global Village-McCluhan.
19	The Little Review <i>Ulysses</i> , Fweet.
20	Fweet, Hayman's "First Draft Version," and <i>How Joyce Wrote 'Finnegans Wake'</i> are all useful for genetic stuff.
21	Really too many to list: The original <i>JJA</i> , various published transcriptions of manuscripts and notebooks in books and periodicals.
22	<i>JJA</i> + Brepols FW Notebooks + Fweet.
23	fweet.org, https://johngordonfinnegan.weebly.com/ .
24	A number of printed editions, if I am reading and need clarification I go to the JJDA.
25	McHugh's Annotations to <i>Finnegans Wake</i> ; Gifford's Annotations to <i>Ulysses</i> .
26	<i>JJA</i> .
27	(1) <i>JJA</i> . (2) The <i>Finnegans Wake</i> Notebooks at Buffalo (Brepols).
28	The different Lexicons, for example, and the Annotations by McHugh.
29	Books, personal notes, old letters.
30	<i>Finnegans Wake</i> Annotations, FWEET.org, Glasheen's Census.
31	Scans of MSS, the printed <i>JJA</i> , Gabler, Rosenbach.
32	Not printed, but FINWAKE (Sinisa Stojakovic in Serbia) and FWEET (Raphael Slep on in the US). Also Michael O'Kelly's compendium of annotations for the James Joyce Institute in Dublin.
33	FWEET http://www.fweet.org ; First Draft Version; www.finwake.com ; John Gordon's Blog; Finnegans Wiki; Gael: A Gaelic Lexicon for Finnegans Wake; A Classical Lexicon for <i>Finnegans Wake</i> ; Adele Glasheen, Third Census of <i>Finnegans Wake</i> ; A Lexicon of the German in <i>Finnegans Wake</i> ; Tindall, A Reader's Guide to <i>Finnegans Wake</i> ; Campbell, A Skeleton Key to <i>Finnegans Wake</i> ; the Oxford English Dictionary; plus Google search.
34	Roland McHugh's Annotations to <i>Finnegans Wake</i> .
35	FINWAKE, McHugh, Campbell and Robinson, Epstein, <i>JJQ</i> , <i>JJ Annual</i> .
36	<i>JJA</i> .

7. Please, rate your experience with the JJDA in terms of accessibility and ease of navigation. [Is the edition freely accessible? Can you easily navigate your way around? What about web accessibility and user friendliness of the edition?]

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Response Total			
1	Very dissatisfied		1.61% 1			
2	Dissatisfied		1.61% 1			
3	Neutral		16.13% 10			
4	Satisfied		51.61% 32			
5	Very satisfied		29.03% 18			
Analysis	Minimum:	1.00	Mean: 4.05	Std. Deviation: 0.81	answered	62
	Maximum:	5.00	Variance: 0.66	Std. Error: 0.10		
	Satisfaction Rate:	76.21				skipped

Comments (optional): (17)

- 1 The JJDA can be quite unforgiving for those not already familiar with the archive and the nitty-gritty of how Joyce writes.
- 2 There are also linking issues fairly regularly, such as where a highlighted part of the text links to a completely unrelated notebook entry rather than the correct entry.
- 3 Mobile app can be a bit iffy, but it's great on a PC. Rose & O'Hanlon's magnum opus.
- 4 Could be more user-friendly.
- 5 They need more accessibility and more interactivity, with hyperlinks that link you directly to notebook sources.
- 6 The navigation is idiosyncratic, but not difficult to work with once you are attuned to the site's structure. Prior knowledge of Joyce's manuscript materials (especially for the sub-chapter structures of *Finnegans Wake* drafts and pre-publications) is possibly indispensable for understanding the genetic evolution of the text. The lack of a search on the site is probably its main drawback for user accessibility.
- 7 If I recall it took a fair while to intuit what various annotations, etc., meant.
- 8 It definitely takes some getting used to: not SUPER user-friendly, but I think that's because the material is so complicated!
- 9 Things can always be better. But the digital availability of so much of this material is unsurpassed. When legally permitted, the complete notebooks would even further enhance this aspect.
- 10 Some editorial marks (e.g. those identifying *FW* draft versions) are too obscure and not well documented. Not having references to *JJA* volume:pages makes it very hard to evaluate *FW* editorial changes.
- 11 It is so easy to use and I am not greatly computer literate.

7. Please, rate your experience with the JJDA in terms of accessibility and ease of navigation. [Is the edition freely accessible? Can you easily navigate your way around? What about web accessibility and user friendliness of the edition?]

- 12 It is very accessible, navigation is good and easy to use in particular notes and links to available external resources are very useful when there. Sometimes there is a misalignment between a note and the draft levels.
- 13 General navigation is OK, but there is quite a bit of room for improvement. (a) In the *FW* section of the edition, the *Finn's Hotel* protodrafts are separate from the drafts for *Work in Progress* so that they are difficult to correlate. (b) The Episodes menu mixes draft analysis (draft stages) with manuscript type (proto-drafts, proofs, etc.), which can be confusing. Also you need a good working knowledge of the draft analysis in order to properly navigate the stages.
- 14 It is obviously useful place to start or check your own work, but it is not peer-reviewed, uses eccentric terms, and is certainly not easy to navigate. It looks and works in amateurish ways.
- 15 Navigation was tricky to learn and could certainly be improved, but [...] I have no idea how those improvements might be effected.
- 16 I have only used it up to page *FW* 115 mostly for the JJ Notebook entries and comments. These I find useful to give some insight into word meaning, authorial intention. I also use Chickenfeed to review my own translation/paraphrase of the text. This, of course, I often disagree with.
- 17 Idiosyncratic editorial apparatus ("matrix", etc.) makes genetic tracing more difficult than it needs to be. There are a number of transcription errors, etc., that are a hindrance. Continued non-publication of Notebook transcriptions is very regrettable.

8. Please, rate your experience with the edited texts and the editorial methodology. [Do you trust the editors' methods? Do you find their methods trustworthy and thorough? Is there a description of the aims and methods of the JJDA? If not, is this self-evident from the content and its presentation?]

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Response Total					
1	Very dissatisfied		3.17% 2					
2	Dissatisfied		7.94% 5					
3	Neutral		28.57% 18					
4	Satisfied		44.44% 28					
5	Very satisfied		15.87% 10					
Analysis	Minimum:	1.00	Mean:	3.62	Std. Deviation:	0.95	answered	63
	Maximum:	5.00	Variance:	0.90	Std. Error:	0.12		
	Satisfaction Rate:	65.48					skipped	0

Comments (optional): (18)

8. Please, rate your experience with the edited texts and the editorial methodology. [Do you trust the editors' methods? Do you find their methods trustworthy and thorough? Is there a description of the aims and methods of the JJDA? If not, is this self-evident from the content and its presentation?]

- | | |
|----|--|
| 1 | Some of the editors' idiosyncratic theories are baked into the site in ways that might not be immediately obvious to users. |
| 2 | The results seem sound, overall, but down to the nitty-gritty, there are a lot of methodological questions to be asked. Also, the division of writing stages is hard to follow. In the end, you have to recheck everything yourself. The JJDA is what is and says it is, an archive, not an edition, though they surreptitiously claim so, of course. But as an archive, it is top of the bill. |
| 3 | The "notons" are not accessible; they list sources by matrix in an unknown configuration that is difficult to link to the documents, leaving editorial decisions somewhat obscure. Rose's decision to use his own "names" for the various documents rather than those they are known by in other sources creates a confusing and opaque editing process. It is not always clear when he has made an editorial decision without textual support vs. with support, or why he has made those decisions. |
| 4 | Extensive evidence of meticulous work; lots of documentation; not much discussion of methodology. |
| 5 | I understand some of the controversies concerning their editions and isotext constructions, but without serious training in the field, I rely on the judgements of experts. |
| 6 | Declared editorial aims irrelevant to range of actual and possible uses. |
| 7 | The JJDA prefers to use its own referencing system (for manuscripts and notebooks) as well as using the page numbers corresponding to the editors' own versions of the text (rather than the texts widely used by the Joyce community)—again, this is idiosyncratic, but does not compromise the trustworthiness and thoroughness of the materials presented. |
| 8 | I am satisfied with anything that permits me to see the process of editorial decision-making. |
| 9 | I might not agree with all the editorial choices, but I wouldn't expect everyone to agree with all editorial choices I would make. |
| 10 | Though understandable, the focus on the 2010 <i>FW</i> edition over the 1939 one is not too convenient. Even with the JJDA, it is hard to make informed decisions about the 2010 editorial changes (especially with no <i>JJA</i> volume:page draft references). Worst of all, some editorial changes are extended through all drafts, including those where they are absent, making the JJDA draft transcriptions somewhat untrustworthy. |
| 11 | The depth is amazing. |
| 12 | I do not always trust their final choices but always clear that it is done with consideration. Would like to see better explanation of choices when they are made, but that might be a very large task. It is clear, however, that the choices are linked to the Rose/O'Hanlon publications. On methodology, it is not always clear if the decisions on levels within a draft stage and links to the archive would assist. |

8. Please, rate your experience with the edited texts and the editorial methodology. [Do you trust the editors' methods? Do you find their methods trustworthy and thorough? Is there a description of the aims and methods of the JJDA? If not, is this self-evident from the content and its presentation?]

- 13 I do trust the editors' judgment. Having worked on the *FW* manuscripts for quite a long time, I have found very few errors or places of disagreement. However, a significant drawback of the edition is that there is no complete editorial rationale. Anyone who hasn't worked with the *JJA* will find it challenging to orient themselves. The Isotext also presents its challenges. On the one hand, there is no quick guide or overview of the diacritics; on the other hand, the screen layout is less than satisfactory, and the diacritics in particular are hard to read.

- 14 I mainly use the website as a way to access and understand the notebooks.

- 15 There is no overarching description of methods and procedures. It is an unprofessional take it or leave it venture. It is what it is.

- 16 I am a fan of the whole project.

- 17 I have chosen not to engage with the idea of an improved text, accepting its imperfect and unfinishable nature.

- 18 Please see comments above, which cover much of this. There is no description of the aims and methods of the JJDA. And these are far from self-evident from the content and its presentation.

9. Please, rate your experience with the JJDA in terms of its Joyce content. [Do you see any gaps in knowledge or omissions of Joyce material? Is there anything important missing from the edition (e.g., images, transcriptions, full texts, comments, context material, bibliography etc.)? Is any omission explained and/or justified?]

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Response Total					
1	Very dissatisfied	0.00%	0					
2	Dissatisfied	3.28%	2					
3	Neutral	18.03%	11					
4	Satisfied	49.18%	30					
5	Very satisfied	29.51%	18					
Analysis	Minimum:	2.00	Mean:	4.05	Std. Deviation:	0.78	answered	61
	Maximum:	5.00	Variance:	0.60	Std. Error:	0.10		
	Satisfaction Rate:	76.23					skipped	2

Comments (optional): (18)

- 1 The JJDA is not only the best resource for archival Joyce content; it is the only resource.

- 2 The leading questions (“Do you see any gaps”, etc.) are well posed and valid. Of course, the Wakey, and Joyce in general, always wants more...

9. Please, rate your experience with the JJDA in terms of its Joyce content. [Do you see any gaps in knowledge or omissions of Joyce material? Is there anything important missing from the edition (e.g., images, transcriptions, full texts, comments, context material, bibliography etc.)? Is any omission explained and/or justified?]

3	I wish more of the notebook transcriptions were available on the website; many are still under copyright, from my understanding.
4	Gaps are to be expected, especially as regards to contextual materials. I used to miss images (of published versions), but there are more and more of them.
5	Occasionally there's notebook material they can't present, but it's always explained. Their incorporation of Herring's transcriptions is especially great.
6	For textual content, the JJDA is very comprehensive. Usually, I double check the <i>JJA</i> facsimile reproductions to understand the manuscript presentation and might refer to this for contextual information about a draft material too. Although you can sometimes come across small errors, in my experience, the editors have been very grateful to incorporate user feedback/corrections. Unavailable transcriptions are always explained.
7	Not qualified to answer this question.
8	High quality scans of the notebooks and manuscripts would of course be great, but I don't think the JJDA editors themselves have access to this.
9	The <i>FW</i> "notons" linking notebook sources and <i>FW</i> text are absolutely invaluable. I really miss the option to browse the <i>FW</i> notebooks (almost all B notebooks carry the sad "This annotated notebook transcription is not publicly available at this time" notice). There are occasional errors (which I report), but these are completely understandable in a project of this size.
10	I especially appreciate reference to the Gabler edition and standard <i>Wake</i> edition in addition to Rose/O'Hanlon's own work.
11	I would like more photographs and related paintings to further illustrate the text.
12	Would like better inclusion of full texts that matched significant published editions, e.g., Gabler and the periodicals <i>Little Review</i> and <i>transition</i> . Search function for notes would be useful and, perhaps, an incorporation of word search index.
13	The obvious omission is the absence of digital facsimiles, but equally the digitization of the MSS would be a massive undertaking. The JJDA does have explanations on how the edition can be used, however.
14	This is much too large a question.
15	I might reference the "matrix" mentioned above or other sources of annotations. I am concerned that, as what seems to be essentially an "auteur project" like <i>Finwake</i> and <i>FWEET</i> , it doesn't appear to have the institutional backing to still be around in thirty years. That would be a loss.
16	I do not know. The Joyce universe is too big I would suspect.
17	See comment about Notebook transcriptions. I think this is partly explained by legal considerations, but this is not clarified and remains unsatisfactory. In an ideal world, one would like images and context, but one does realise that providing

9. Please, rate your experience with the JJDA in terms of its Joyce content. [Do you see any gaps in knowledge or omissions of Joyce material? Is there anything important missing from the edition (e.g., images, transcriptions, full texts, comments, context material, bibliography etc.)? Is any omission explained and/or justified?]

some of this is very challenging. It does not set out to provide annotations as such, though it sometimes does in a puzzlingly inconsistent way.

18 I use mainly the episodes' summaries, and sometimes they are not as complete as they could be, but hey! I find that in all my sources.

10. How would you rate the learning curve of the JJDA?

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Response Total					
1	No practice is needed whatsoever.		9.68% 6					
2	There is a learning curve, but it did not take long to acclimatise.		51.61% 32					
3	It is somewhat difficult, even with the explanations.		22.58% 14					
4	It is somewhat difficult since I did not find the key to annotations.		4.84% 3					
5	I did find the key to annotations, but it was not particularly illuminating.		3.23% 2					
6	I still do not understand half of it.		8.06% 5					
Analysis	Minimum:	1.00	Mean:	2.65	Std. Deviation:	1.30	answered	62
	Maximum:	6.00	Variance:	1.68	Std. Error:	0.16		
	Satisfaction Rate:	32.90					skipped	1

I have more to add: (10)

- 1 I still do not understand half of it, but I trust it is the less important half.
- 2 The draft levels, matrices, and document types/names in “notons” are not easy to understand.
- 3 The contents of the appendices are somewhat arbitrary. Now that (links to) images of published versions have been added in the appendices, image links could be added to the draft analysis, too.
- 4 Not necessarily for beginners, but once you have some context, it’s not too difficult to navigate the site.
- 5 The answer obviously depends on user experience.

10. How would you rate the learning curve of the JJDA?

6	I was guided through navigating and using the JJDA by my supervisor in a few 1-2 hour sessions (i.e. help from an experienced user was very useful).
7	It is so easy to use.
8	It is too eccentric and unprofessional. It is not explained well or fully. I feel sorry for most users who are not already familiar with the material, the issues, the background of the editors and their project, etc.
9	It is tricky. Some “Youtube style” online tutorials would be a great advantage.
10	I do not know what else there is in the JJDA concerning <i>FW</i> to discover.

11. Have you noticed any typos, mistakes, or inaccuracies in the transcriptions or the edited texts?

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Response Total
1	No. I haven't noticed anything wrong.		60.32% 38
2	Yes; some occasional typos and such. No big deal.		22.22% 14
3	Yes. I am keeping a list!		17.46% 11
4	The mistakes are actually grave and the editors should be notified.		0.00% 0
Analysis	Minimum:	1.00	Mean: 1.57
	Maximum:	3.00	Std. Deviation: 0.77
	Satisfaction Rate:	19.05	Variance: 0.59
		Std. Error: 0.10	answered: 63
			skipped: 0

12. Is the absence of manuscript reproductions a serious concern for you?

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Response Total
1	Yes, it keeps me up at night.		12.90% 8
2	Yes, but I can manage without them for now.		41.94% 26
3	They could be a nice addition to the JJDA, but hardly make a big difference.		38.71% 24

12. Is the absence of manuscript reproductions a serious concern for you?

4	Manuscripts? What manuscripts?		6.45%	4				
Analysis	Minimum:	1.00	Mean:	2.39	Std. Deviation:	0.79	answered	62
	Maximum:	4.00	Variance:	0.62	Std. Error:	0.10		
	Satisfaction Rate:	46.24					skipped	1

Comments (optional): (12)

- 1 The time and resource overheads required to include manuscript reproductions would be the end of the JJDA. Rose and O'Hanlon are among the best transcribers of Joyce's hand. When I find typos and mistakes in the transcriptions (see Q. 11), which is not often, I write to the editors with suggestions and queries. They are very responsive.
- 2 There's the *JJA*, but in print practically inaccessible, PDFs circulate for the lucky few. Still, they are B/W (bitmapped) and full colour reproductions would be nice, thank you.
- 3 I am lucky because I have access to the *JJA*, but otherwise this would keep me up at night indeed.
- 4 Notebooks would be an excellent resource.
- 5 There are links to the NLI. Copyright restrictions apply to most others. *JJA* makes most others available.
- 6 I usually use the facsimile reproductions alongside the JJDA, but I don't think they are integral to the JJDA as a resource.
- 7 Copyright concerns prevent much useful reproduction.
- 8 That would be great.
- 9 Incorporation of the *JJA* and other sources would be ideal. Without, there should at least be page references.
- 10 I have always referred to original MSS whenever possible (e.g., in British Library, in NLI Dublin, in HRHRC Austin, TX when I was able to travel in person; microfiche was out of the question, photocopies—ditto; it is essential to see the holographs, colours of ink/pencil, and types of paper used.
- 11 I'd love for the manuscripts to be added.
- 12 I do not rely on the edition directly, so I sleep well enough. It is simply useful as a shortcut or to check my own work.

13. Please, pick one or more potential features you would find useful in the JJDA:

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Response Total					
1	a simple and/or complex search interface		72.58% 45					
2	content index or site map for navigation		50.00% 31					
3	citation and/or other bibliographic tools		32.26% 20					
4	other export formats (eBook, PDF, XML)		38.71% 24					
5	access to basic data, i.e., raw code (XML, etc.)		16.13% 10					
6	options for annotations, commentary notes and personalisation		27.42% 17					
7	Other (please specify):		17.74% 11					
Analysis	Minimum:	1.00	Mean:	3.11	Std. Deviation:	1.95	answered	62
	Maximum:	7.00	Variance:	3.81	Std. Error:	0.16	skipped	1

Other (please specify): (11)

1	The JJDA is not written in XML. This is an important point that bears on the success of the site but also reflects its limitations.
2	O dear! Let's first brush up and update (and correct) what is there, in the Beast, before adding features.
3	A prominent discussion of editorial principles and methods.
4	Open-source version control. Collaborative editing.
5	Content index already available.
6	Better explanation of editorial marks (e.g. those used for <i>FW</i> drafts). References to <i>JJA</i> volume:page for <i>FW</i> drafts. Access to <i>FW</i> notebook transcriptions.
7	As before, I would love to have photographs, manuscripts: a parade of here-comes-everybody all in one place, constantly evolving.
8	See earlier comments on incorporating significant published texts. On annotations, ideally the incorporation of significant quality external resources such as FINWAKE and JJON would be useful.
9	My priority would be the option for Reading Groups to add their discoveries.
10	Perhaps my failure to suggest anything indicates that the JJDA has appeared less promising to explore.

13. Please, pick one or more potential features you would find useful in the JJDA:

11 I'm not an advanced computer user so am more than happy with what it is and how it works.

14. Have you had an occasion to contact the editors? If yes, please, qualify your experience.

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Response Total			
1	No.		77.42% 48			
2	Yes. My suggestions were taken into consideration.		17.74% 11			
3	Yes. My suggestion was dismissed but with a good explanation as to why.		0.00% 0			
4	Yes. But I got no response to my email.		1.61% 1			
5	I did not know one could get in touch with the editors. How do you do it?		3.23% 2			
Analysis	Minimum:	1.00	Mean: 1.35	Std. Deviation: 0.84	answered	62
	Maximum:	5.00	Variance: 0.71	Std. Error: 0.11		
	Satisfaction Rate:	8.87			skipped	1

Comments (optional): (8)

- 1 I have shared a lot of my own research with the editors. They are – or, before John’s death, were—very responsive.
- 2 The editor in charge of the Beast died a year ago, the very attentive John O’Hanlon. What will be now is a big question. The more people engage, the better, of course.
- 3 The site has been regularly updated to include comments from a number of users up to the death of John O’Hanlon.
- 4 I want to contact them, but don’t know how.
- 5 Both John and Danis were very kind and responsive. Sad about John...
- 6 I tend to avoid the lunatic fringe as much as possible.
- 7 I was kindly granted permission to use the restored text for a public event on Zoom. Thanks again!
- 8 I never thought to do so.

15. Have you or would you recommend the JJDA to your students or fellow Joyceans?

Answer Choices		Response Percent	Response Total					
1	Absolutely, it should be in every Joyce syllabus.		51.61% 32					
2	Yes, I do not see how it could hurt.		33.87% 21					
3	Yes, but it is a matter of taste.		9.68% 6					
4	Maybe. But I will voice my reservations if I do.		4.84% 3					
5	Probably not.		0.00% 0					
Analysis	Minimum:	1.00	Mean:	1.68	Std. Deviation:	0.84	answered	62
	Maximum:	4.00	Variance:	0.70	Std. Error:	0.11		
	Satisfaction Rate:	16.94					skipped	1

Comments (optional): (11)

- 1 I would recommend the JJDA to anyone getting into Joyce manuscripts. With my own students, I have helped them to adapt to the edition and to learn to work with it but also caution them about its limitations.
- 2 That is not to say that the word of the JJDA is Holy Scripture of course.
- 3 I certainly make my own students use it.
- 4 Please release the JJDA on GitHub or equivalent.
- 5 Thanks for making this great resource available!
- 6 Choices very curiously phrased to elicit emotional rather than factual reactions.
- 7 As a genetic Joycean, it is especially useful to me, but I cannot judge the overall interest of other scholars.
- 8 Thanks for the contact. Our reading group has been working from a re-typeset edition of *FW* that is easier to read, but, alas, not easier to understand. We read mostly for the sound and the challenge and the fun.
- 9 It has its drawbacks one should be aware of, but it is still an invaluable resource.
- 10 It was a great help hunting how and when some words got into *FW* and the *FW* Chicken Guide strikes me as one of the best summaries of the book that I have read.
- 11 Although far from perfect—see above—it is still a huge advance on any previous textual treatment of *FW*. The only comparable exercise would be in GJS, and this is far more comprehensive. Once again, the absence of *FW* Notebook transcriptions is the main drawback.